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Review Article

**DETERMINATION OF THE SPECIFIC ROTATION OF AN
OPTICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES BY USING
POLARIMETER**Rushikesh Ankush Dhanve¹, Yogiraj Prakash Muley², Sanket Anil Ingle³¹Department of Bachelor of Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Technological University, Raigad, Maharashtra²Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Technological University, Raigad, Maharashtra³Department of Bachelor of Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Technological University, Raigad, Maharashtra**Abstract:**

A half-shade polarimeter is an optical instrument used to measure the optical rotation of substances, typically liquid solutions containing optically active compounds. These compounds have the ability to rotate the plane of polarization of linearly polarized light, a property that can be exploited to determine the concentration, purity, or specific rotation of the substance.

Light waves are a form of electromagnetic radiation, consisting of oscillating electric and magnetic fields. In natural light, these oscillations occur in all possible planes perpendicular to the direction of propagation. Polarization is the process of filtering out light waves so that they only oscillate in a single plane, producing linearly polarized light. There are several methods for achieving polarization, including reflection, refraction, and absorption. In the case of Laurent's Half-Shade Polarimeter, polarization is achieved using a polarizer, typically a Nicol prism or a polarizing film, which transmits light waves oscillating in a single plane while absorbing or reflecting the others.

Because light-field and polarization information contain much information of scenes, light-field and polarization imaging-systems can be used, e.g., for target detection, material classification, and biological analysis. However, most conventional systems rely on scanning or camera arrays, which tend to make the system both bulky and unstable. Here, we investigate a novel approach, snapshot polarimetry, volumetric imaging (SPVI), which introduces micro-polarization elements into the paradigmatic focused light-field imaging system. SPVI can simultaneously capture and reconstruct the light-field and polarization information of a scene using a single detector. The validity and accuracy of SPVI are determined via Stoke-parameter measurements and depth measurements. Compared to conventional polarimetric light-field imagers, SPVI excels with respect to compactness, robustness, and low cost. Moreover, this tool might enable new possibilities for polarimetric 3D analysis.

Key words : Analyzer, Dextrorotatory, Optically active, Polarimeter, Polarizer, Specific rotation, Plan polarized light

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Let us have a look at what optical rotation is. So, optical activity or optical rotation is the ability of a compound to rotate the plane of polarized light, and the compounds having this ability to rotate the plane of polarized light are known as optically active materials. The optical rotation of substances is due to the interaction of the electromagnetic radiation of polarized light with the un-symmetric electric fields generated by the electrons in a chiral molecule. Optical activity is usually found in organic substances. For example, the sugar solution is optically active, it exhibits optical rotation on observing through the polarimeter. Other examples of optically active substances are turpentine, sodium chlorate, cinnabar, etc...

Any substance or compound is said to be optically active when the linearly polarized light is being rotated when it is passing through it. The optical rotation or optical activity is the angle through which the plane of polarization is rotated when polarized light passes through a layer of a liquid (such as sugar solution or in other words diluted sugar solution). Optical rotation is the effect that is determined by the concentration of chiral molecules and their molecular structure in a substance. Every optically active substance will have its specific rotation. Depending on the concentration level the optical activity will be either increasing or decreasing.

In 1811, French physicist Francious Arega observed that when a plane polarised light passed through some materials in particular through some crystals such as quartz, the plane of emerging light is not the same as the plane of the incident light. These crystals rotated the plane of polarization of incident light. This phenomenon of rotation is known as an optical activity or optical rotation. The substances that exhibit such rotations are known as optically active substances. To understand what is optical activity or optical rotation we will explain a unique experiment. The optical rotation is measured through a polarimeter. The optical activity of optically active substances is studied by the polarimeter. Polarimetry Gives the measurement of rotation of plane-polarized light by an optically active substance.

2. Research problem :-

In polarimetry, we aim to determine the specific rotation of an optically active substance using a polarimeter. The specific rotation is a property that characterizes how much a substance rotates the plane of polarized light. Our goal is to find the specific

rotation of the solution by measuring the rotation angle produced when polarized light passes through the solution.

3. Hypothesis Statement:-

Let's consider a plane-polarized monochromatic light of wavelength λ passing through a solution containing an optically active substance. The plane of polarization of the light is rotated through an angle θ . By measuring the rotation angle for known concentrations, we can determine the specific rotation of an unknown solution.

4. METHODOLOGY:

4.1 Introduction of Polarimetry :-

A polarimeter is a scientific instrument used to measure optical rotation: the angle of rotation caused by passing linearly polarized light through an optically active substance.

Some chemical substances are optically active, and linearly polarized (uni-directional) light will rotate either to the left (counter-clockwise) or right (clockwise) when passed through these substances. The amount by which the light is rotated is known as the *angle of rotation*. The direction (clockwise or counterclockwise) and magnitude of the rotation reveals information about the sample's chiral properties such as the relative concentration of enantiomers present in the sample.

Most physical properties of enantiomers i.e., melting point, boiling point, refractive index, etc. are identical. However, they differ in a property called optical activity, in which a sample rotates the plane of polarization of a polarized light beam passing through. This effect was first discovered in 1808 by E.L. Malus (1775-1812), who passed light through reflective glass surfaces. Four years later, J.B. Biot (1774-1862) found that the extent of rotation of the light depends on the thickness of the quartz plates that he used. He also discovered that other compounds i.e., turpentine and sucrose solutions were capable of rotating the light. He attributed this "optical activity" to certain features in their molecular structure (asymmetry). Based on his research, he designed one of the first polariscopes, and formulated the basic quantitative laws of polarimetry. In 1850, Wilhelmy used polarimetry to study the reaction rate of the hydrolysis of sucrose. In 1874, van't Hoff proposed that a tetrahedral environment of the carbon atom could explain the phenomenon of optical activity. Today, polarimetry is used routinely in quality and process control in the pharmaceutical industry, the flavor, fragrance and essential oil industry, the food industry, and the chemical industry. The optical purity of the product can be determined by

measuring the specific rotation of compounds like amino acids, antibiotics, steroids, vitamins, lemon oil, various sugars, and polymers and comparing them with the reference value (if the specific rotation of the pure enantiomer is known).

- Polarimetry involves measuring the polarization state of radiation. Unlike intensity measurements alone, polarimetry provides astrophysical information by considering the polarization of light.
- All sources of radiation, whether in the lab or the sky, exhibit some degree of polarization. Even a completely unpolarized source is likely unachievable.
- Fractional polarizations of interest to astronomers can range from tenths to parts per million.
- The physical basis of polarization involves various mechanisms, including scattering, differential absorption, and direct radiation processes.

4.2 History :-

The Laurent's Half-Shade Polarimeter has an intriguing history that dates back to the mid-19th century. Let's explore its origins and the scientific contributions of the French scientist Augustin-Jean Fresnel.

A polarimeter is a scientific instrument used to measure optical rotation: the angle of rotation caused by passing linearly polarized light through an optically active substance.

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The rotation of the orientation of linearly polarized light was first observed in 1811 in quartz by French physicist François Arago. In 1820, the English astronomer Sir John F.W. Herschel discovered that different individual quartz crystals, whose crystalline structures are mirror images of each other (see illustration), rotate linear polarization by equal amounts but in opposite directions. Jean Baptiste Biot also observed the rotation of the axis of polarization in

certain liquids and vapors of organic substances such as turpentine. Simple polarimeters have been used since this time to measure the concentrations of simple sugars, such as glucose, in solution. In fact one name for D-glucose (the biological isomer), is dextrose, referring to the fact that it causes linearly polarized light to rotate to the right or dexter side. In a similar manner, levulose, more commonly known as fructose, causes the plane of polarization to rotate to the left. Fructose is even more strongly levorotatory than glucose is dextrorotatory. In 1849, Louis Pasteur resolved a problem concerning the nature of tartaric acid. A solution of this compound derived from living things (to be specific, wine lees) rotates the plane of polarization of light passing through it, but tartaric acid derived by chemical synthesis has no such effect, even though its reactions are identical and its elemental composition is the same. Pasteur noticed that the crystals come in two asymmetric forms that are mirror images of one another. Sorting the crystals by hand gave two forms of the compound: Solutions of one form rotate polarized light clockwise, while the other form rotate light counterclockwise. An equal mix of the two has no polarizing effect on light

1. Augustin-Jean Fresnel :-

- **Augustin-Jean Fresnel** was a remarkable figure in the field of optics and polarization during the 19th century.
- His groundbreaking work included the development of the **Fresnel lens**, which found applications in lighthouses, cameras, and other optical devices.
- Fresnel's lens design significantly improved the efficiency of light collection and distribution, making it a crucial advancement for maritime safety and photography.

2. Wave Theory of Light :-

- Fresnel is best known for his contributions to the **wave theory of light**.
- He proposed that light behaves as a wave, rather than a particle, which challenged the prevailing corpuscular theory.
- His wave theory explained phenomena such as diffraction, interference, and polarization, laying the foundation for modern optics.

3. Laurent's Half-Shade Polarimeter :-

- The half-shade polarimeter owes its name to Fresnel's pioneering work.
- It was developed as an extension of his research on light polarization and interference.
- The instrument aimed to provide more precise and sensitive measurements of **optical rotation** in substances.

Fig.1 Half-shade polarimetry

4.3 Types of polarimetry :-

- Laurent's half-shade polarimeter
- Biquartz polarimeter
- Lippich polarimeter
- Quartz-wedge polarimeter
- Manual
- Semi-automatic
- Fully-automatic.

5. Principle :-

Polarimetry can be defined as the analysis of the rotation of polarized light by transparent components. Polarimetry is a sensitive and non-destructive technique for measuring the optical activity of organic and inorganic compounds. If linearly polarized light

rotates as it passes, a compound is assumed to be optically active.

The basic operating principle of a polarimeter includes a source that produces light with a specifically prepared linear polarization state, usually by passing through a polarizer. The light is transmitted by an optically active sample which often rotates the direction of polarization. After passing through the sample, another measurement of the angle of polarization modified by the light transfer by analysis, which can be rotated around the axis of the beam. The simplest technique is to move the analyzer to where optical power transmission is lowest.

PRINCIPLE

5.1 . Instrumentation :-

Construction :-

Fig.2 Construction of polarimetry

Operating principle of an optical polarimeter.

1. Light source
2. Un-polarized light
3. Linear polarizer
4. Linearly polarized light
5. Sample tube containing chiral molecules under study
6. Optical rotation due to molecules
7. Rotatable linear analyzer
8. Detector

- Linearly polarized light from the source passes through the Nicol prism (polarizer).
- The half-shade device (H) splits the polarized light into two halves.
- One half is illuminated, while the other remains darkened.
- The sample holder contains the optically active substance under study.
- The analyzer, positioned after the sample, can be rotated.
- The intensity of light passing through the sample depends on its optical rotation.
- By adjusting the analyzer, we can find the angle at which the transmitted light intensity is maximum or minimum.

This angle corresponds to the optical rotation caused by the sample.

5.2 Working :-

1. The light source emits monochromatic light, which passes through the polarizer to produce linearly polarized light.
2. The polarized light enters the sample cell containing the optically active substance. As the light passes through the substance, its plane of polarization is rotated by an angle proportional to the concentration, purity, or specific rotation of the substance.
3. The rotated polarized light then passes through the half-shade device, which splits the field of view into two halves with different intensities, depending on the rotation angle of the plane of polarization.
4. The light continues through the analyzer, which further modifies the intensities of the two halves of the field of view based on its orientation relative to the plane of polarization.
5. The observer looks through the eyepiece and adjusts the angular scale until the boundary between the two halves of the field of view is aligned with the reference mark. The rotation angle of the plane of polarization can then be read from the scale.
6. The measured rotation angle is used to calculate the concentration, purity, or specific rotation of the optically active substance, based on a

known relationship between these properties and the optical rotation.

5.3 Advantages of polarimetry :-

1. **Ease of Use:** Polarimetry is an easy-to-use technique that doesn't require experts to operate. It's accessible even to those without specialized training.
2. **Stability:** A polarimeter is not affected by changes in laser intensity. This stability ensures consistent and reliable measurements.
3. **Temperature and pH Control:** The temperature and pH inside the eye remain stable during polarimetric measurements. This controlled environment contributes to accurate results.
4. **Wide Range of Emission Wavelengths:** Advanced versions of polarimeters offer a wide range of emission wavelengths compared to conventional light sources. This flexibility allows for versatile applications.
5. **Profitable Technique:** The analysis with a polarimeter is very easy and fast, making it a profitable technique for various scientific and industrial purposes.

5.4 Disadvantage of polarimetry:

1. **Sample Volume and Concentration:** To determine the specific and optical rotation of a substance, large sample volumes with high concentrations are required. This can be a limitation when dealing with limited sample quantities.
2. **Limited Applicability:** The main disadvantage of polarimetry is that it can only analyze optically active components. If a substance is not optically active (does not rotate the plane of polarization), polarimetry cannot provide meaningful results.
3. **Low Sensitivity:** Compared to other analytical techniques, polarimetry has lower sensitivity. It may not be suitable for detecting small changes or low concentrations.
4. **Sensitivity to Motion and Scattering:** Polarimetry is very sensitive to movement and dispersion. Any vibrations or disturbances during measurements can affect the accuracy of results.

5.5 Applications of Polarimetry :-

- Determination of the purity and concentration of ingredients in pharmaceuticals
- Maturity testing of agricultural products
- Measurement of the sugar content in beverages and candies
- Determination of specific rotation and optical rotation of products such as amino acids, cocaine, antibiotics, dextrose, carbohydrates, analgesics, vitamins, steroids, sugars, serums, diuretics, and codeine, etc.
- Structural determination

Fig.3 Experimental samples in beaker

6. Experimental Methodology:-

Aim :- To determine the specific rotation of an optically active substance by using polarimeter.

Material Requirement :-

Instrument :- Polarimetry

Apparatus :-

- Optically active substance
- Measuring cylinder
- Beaker
- Scale
- Sodium light source
- Sturrer

Chemicals :-

-Distilled water

-Sugar solution(sucrose)

-Unknown solution

Procedure/Working:-

1. Clean the polarimeter tube, beaker, flask, and measuring cylinder with water.
2. Fill the polarimeter tube with distilled water and observe uniform illumination positions.
3. Choose one of the weak uniform illuminations accurately and note the angle of rotation on the scale.

4. Prepare a solution of known concentration by dissolving a known amount of the active substance in distilled water.
5. Fill the polarimeter tube with the solution and note the rotation produced by adjusting the scale.
6. Repeat steps 3, 4, and 5 for different concentrations.
7. Plot a graph of θ (rotation angle) versus concentration.
8. Use the calibration curve to find the concentration of an unknown solution

Key points:-

- The calibration curve relates rotation angle to concentration.
- Specific rotation (s) can be determined from the table.

Fig.4 Experimental result**Observation Table :-**

Analyzer reading with distilled water:

Clockwise			Anti-clockwise			Mean
Main Scale	Vernier scale	Total (x)	Main scale	Vernier scale	Total (y)	$\theta_1 = \frac{x+y}{2}$
52	2	52.2	232	1	232.1	$= \frac{52.2+232.1}{2}$ $=142.15$

Table.no.1

Analyzer reading with sugar solution:

Clockwise			Anti-clockwise			Mean
Main scale	Vernier scale	Total (x)	Main scale	Vernier scale	Total (y)	$\theta_2 = \frac{x + y}{2}$ $= \frac{71.4 + 250.3}{2}$ $= 160.85$
71	4	71.4	250	3	250.3	

Table.no.2

Calculations:-

$$\theta_1 = 142.15$$

$$\theta_2 = 160.85$$

$$\theta = \theta_1 - \theta_2 /$$

$$= 142.15 - 160.85$$

$$\theta = 18.7^\circ$$

Least count and reading observation:

$$\text{Least count} = \frac{\text{a smaller division on main scale}}{\text{total number of division on vernier scale}}$$

$$= \frac{2}{20} = 0.1$$

- Length of polarimeter tube = 20 cm (2 dm)
- Conc. Of solute = 10%
- Least count = 0.1
- Sugar = 20 gm
- Distilled water = 100 ml
- Conc. Of sugar solution = 0.166
- Room temperature = 25°
- Lymda (λ) = 589 nm

Optical rotation of given solution:

- Concentration = 10%
- Least count = 0.1
- Length = 2 dm
- $\theta_0 = 0$
- $\theta_1 = 142.15$

Calculation :-

$$\theta_1 = \theta_1 - \theta_0$$

$$= 142.15 - 0$$

$$= 142.15$$

$$\theta_2 = \theta_2 - \theta_0$$

$$= 160.85 - 0$$

$$= 160.85$$

$$\theta = \theta_1 - \theta_2 /$$

$$= 142.15 - 160.85$$

$$\theta = 18.7^\circ$$

Specific rotation of given solution:

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^t = \frac{\theta}{lc} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{18.7}{2 \times 0.166} \times 100$$

$$= 56.32^{\circ}$$

Calculated value = 56.32^o

Actual value = 63.5^o ± 1.3 at 25^oc

Unknown concentration of solution

$$\theta = 18.7^{\circ}$$

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^t = 56.32^{\circ}$$

$$\text{Conc.} = \frac{\theta}{L[\alpha]_{\lambda}^t} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{18.7}{2 \times 56.32} \times 100$$

$$= 16.60 \%$$

Result :-

The specific rotation for cane sugar at a temperature 25^o c is 56.32^o

Standard value is 63.5^o ± 1.3^o

Calibration :

Traditionally, a sucrose solution with a defined concentration was used to calibrate polarimeters relating the amount of sugar molecules to the light polarization rotation. The International Commission for Uniform Methods of Sugar Analysis (ICUMSA) played a key role in unifying analytical methods for the sugar industry, set standards for the International Sugar Scale (ISS) and the specifications for polarimeters in sugar industry—However, sugar solutions are prone to contamination and evaporation. Moreover, the optical rotation of a substance is very sensitive to temperature. A more reliable and stable standard was found: crystalline quartz which is oriented and cut in a way that it matches the optical rotation of a normal sugar solution, but without showing the disadvantages mentioned above. Quartz (silicon dioxide, SiO₂) is a common mineral, a trigonal chemical compound of silicon and oxygen. Nowadays, quartz plates or quartz control plates of different thickness serve as standards to calibrate polarimeters and saccharimeters. In order to ensure reliable and comparable results, quartz plates can be calibrated and certified by metrology institutes. However, Alternatively, calibration may be checked using a Polarization Reference Standard, which consists of a plate of quartz mounted in a holder perpendicular to the light path. These standards are available, traceable to NIST, by contacting Rudolph Research Analytical, located at 55 Newburgh Road, Hackettstown, NJ 07840, USA.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, polarimeters are valuable scientific instruments used to measure the degree of polarization of light. By assessing the rotation of the plane of polarization, polarimeters provide essential information about the properties and characteristics of different substances.

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